
CONCEPT OF VALUE EDUCATION AS PERCEIVED BY SREE SREE THAKUR ANUKUL CHANDRA**Dr. Chittaranjan Nayak***Head, Department of Education**Jagannath Mahavidyalaya, Nayagarh***Dr. S. K. Pradhan***Principal**Nathulal das B.Ed College , Manikpur*

Abstract:

The purpose of this paper is to find out the concept and idea of value education as perceived by Sri Sri Thakur Anukul Chandra and the possibility of using it to pursue value within the field of education. The paper asks how the concept of value education of Sri Sri Thakur Anukul Chandra help professional teachers to impart value education among students in different levels? In what ways can Sri Sri Thakur Anukul's ideas about value education and their effects on the human being help today's students to pursue higher education in the global context? What are the real concept of value education according to Sri Sri Thakur Anukul's praxis in the pursuit of global education? To answer this question, this paper relies on data collected during the author's doctoral research in which he conducted open-ended semi-structured interviews of 20 purposively selected school activists in Odisha 2006 and 2010. This paper calls for a revolutionized reflection of Sri Sri Thakur Anukul on value education. By that, this paper suggests bringing a discursive sophistication into their speeches and writings in ways that can inform and shape contemporary activism while acknowledging their shortcomings and limitations. Furthermore, this paper argues that, given the current scenario of value education that is imparted to the students.

Key Words: Value Education, Sri Sri Thakur Anukul Chandra

Introduction

Education, Sri Sri Thakur holds, to be productive and effective, should aim at formation of right types of concentric habit and behaviour, right types of concentric habit and behaviour, unfoldment of distinctive traits and faculties, disciplining of intellect and powers of reasoning, broadening and deepening of feeling, sympathy, sentiment and interest, cultivation of inquisitiveness and creative research-spirit, unfurlment of efficiency, active skill and constructive ability, inculcation of a genuine desire for perfect conception and constructive ability, inculcation of a genuine desire for perfect conception and thorough execution, improvement of knowledge and wisdom, fostering of self-control, self-denial and self-less service, and development of a consistent character and an integrated, complete personality.

Concept of value education

Value education means inculcation in the children a sense of humanism, a deep concern for the well-being of others and the nation. This can be accomplished only when we instill in the children a deep feeling of commitment to values that would build this country and bring back to the people pride in work that brings order, security and assured progress. Through value education we like to develop the social, moral, aesthetic and spiritual sides of a person which are often undermined in formal education. Value education teaches us to preserve whatever is good and worthwhile in what we have inherited from our culture. It helps us to accept respect the attitude and behaviour of those who differ from us. Value education does not mean value imposition or indoctrination. Value education has the capacity to transform a diseased mind into a very young, fresh, innocent, healthy natural and attentive mind. The transformed mind is capable of higher sensitivity and a heightened level of perception. This leads to fulfillment of the evolutionary role in man and in life.

Value education is more wider, practicable and adoptable than religious education or moral education, as no specific faith or religion is reflected through ethical, moral, social, cultural or spiritual values (Gupta; 1988). Value Education is an approach to inculcate broad-mindedness, tolerance and proper social and emotional qualities. Understood in its broader sense value education aims at training the young in the entire realm of values—physical, emotional, intellectual, imaginative, aesthetic, democratic, scientific, social, moral and spiritual. This can be pursued by any individual irrespective of his practice of any religion or on religion at all. ung people.

Methodology

As it is a philosophical study, content analysis technique and library technique were followed by the researcher. Sree Sree Thakur's literature is vast and deep. Sree Sree Thakur has given various messages in Bengali and English which cover all fields of knowledge, giving rise to solution of human problems in those fields. These messages have been recorded in book forms by Satsang Publishing House, Satsang located at Deoghar (Jharkhand). Some of the books have also been translated into other regional languages.

The researcher made a thorough study of Sree Sree Thakur's literature and collect relevant data. Besides, the researcher made a thorough study of different Ph.D. Theses that have been conducted on the philosophy of Sree Sree Thakur and collected required data. The researcher also collected relevant data and required information from different Journals, Magazines, Periodicals and related books available in Satsang library at Deoghar (Jharkhaand)

In addition to the above methods of data collection, the research worker consulted eminent personalities, having expertise knowledge on Sree Sree Thakur's philosophy and collected relevant data from them. The researcher also collected required informations from various Journals, Magazines, Periodicals and related books available in the libraries of different Satsang Vihars located at different places of India.

Qualitative analysis

Value education, according to Sree Sree Thakur is a full-fledged personality of an individual i.e. an all round development, leading to the development of all aspects of life—physical, mental, emotional, social, moral and spiritual. He finds a lacuna in the Modern Indian Education System as regards the social, moral and spiritual aspects of life. In other words, the Modern Indian Education system does not provide any scope for inculcation of social, moral and spiritual values among the pupils. According to him, the inculcation of these intrinsic values is part and parcel of a sound Education System. That is to say, the modern Indian Education lacks its values (social, moral and spiritual), failing to fulfill the real aim of it. The social, moral and spiritual values lead to the development of organised habits and behaviour, giving rise to self control, self denial and selfless, service which ultimately result into a balanced character. Sree Sree Thakur is of the opinion that Education without good conduct and character is merely an induction of knowledge.

Sree Sree Thakur reveals that good conduct and character leads to the expansion of mind, giving rise to broadening and deepening of feeling, sympathy, sentiment and interest with serviceable attitude that nurtures one's being and becoming to uphill enlightenment. Hence, development of good conduct and character is as essential as the inculcation of knowledge of the objective subjects. An ideal character sprouts into trained habits, behaviour and commonsense which infuse sharp intelligence. Mere acquisition of knowledge is of no value unless it gives rise to a balanced growth of intelligence. Education that does not promote intelligence is not true Education.

Findings and suggestion

Sree Sree Thakur Anukulchandra, the Modern Indian Prophet and the founder of the Satsang has advocated an integral philosophy which is scientific, practical and value-based which is suitable for the modern

scientific world. His educational philosophy is also scientific based, practical, child-centered, broad-based, need-based and value-based which is suitable for the modern Indian Education System. So far the view of Sree Sree Thakur in the perspective of Modern Indian Education is concerned, he recommends for a National System of Education that has been emphasized by the Education Commission (1964-66). Besides, the Education Commission has also pointed out to the erosion of long accepted values throughout the country and recommended for revival of the same through inculcation of social, moral and spiritual values among the students. Sree Sree Thakur has strongly advocated a broad based value education programme which has relevance to the need of Modern Indian Education system as recommended by the Education Commission (1964-66).

But the commission could not have perceptible impact upon our Indian Education system in developing social, moral and spiritual values among the pupils in a desirable manner. As a result, the younger generation of the modern Indian society is hankering after material power and enjoyment. This mad rush for material prosperity induces a passionate craves in the individual, making him obsessed by a selfish exploiting eagerness. Thus the present Indian society is suffering from the hazards of disunity, hypocrisy, treachery, indiscipline, domestic unhappiness, maladjustment, alcoholism, criminality, sectarianism and blood-shed.

Sree Sree Thakur gives a clarion call to impart education on the foundation of social, moral and spiritual values in the pattern of ancient Indian Education. In this regard, he recommends that the learners should be attached to the Living Ideal —the Divine Man of the present through love, worship and admiration and education should centre round the preaching and teachings of the Ideal – the Spiritual Master. When the educands love the Lord fervently with every concentric eagerness, active volition, and sympathetic sustenance, they are tuned in the tune of the Master Beloved with every skilful inquisitive activeness that protects, nurtures and fulfils him. As a result, they can administer themselves with every active meaningful moral zeal to fulfil the Principle making each other friendly,—saintly life smiles there with every flavorful smile. And this love infuses lore with every roaring rhythm with the effulgence of consciousness and far-sighted intelligence.

In the event of the existential crisis of modern India, there is an urgent need of value-based education as propounded by Sree Sree Thakur. Hence, various aspects of education given by Sree Sree Thakur are relevant for Modern Indian Education System.

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